

TAKING NOTES DURING THE TEACHING PROCESS: THE PERSPECTIVE OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS

Maja BOSANAC¹

Gorana VOJČIĆ²

^{1,2}University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract

Since the 1970s, numerous foreign studies have explored the topic of note-taking during the educational process and the benefits it brings to student learning. Given that a large number of studies have focused on students, the aim of this paper is to examine the importance that university teachers attribute to students' note-taking compared to copying teacher notes.. This paper is dedicated to an analysis of one specific item related to note-taking that was included in the Questionnaire: Approaches to Teaching Inventory. The sample consisted of 317 teachers from the University of Novi Sad, representing various scientific fields (natural sciences, humanities and social sciences, technical and technological sciences, medical sciences and arts). In addition to the scientific fields to which the teachers belong, the responses were interpreted in relation to the variables such as gender, age, the level of study at which the teachers teach, their teaching experience, and the size of the teaching group for the given subject. The results suggest that teachers give a slight preference to student note-taking compared to providing

students with ready-made notes, giving a slight preference to student-focused teaching (conceptual change) over teacher-focused instruction (information transmission). Variables related to affiliation with a specific scientific field and the age of the respondents significantly influenced the teachers' responses. However, further research is needed in order to obtain more comprehensive data, and in the contemporary context, it would be particularly important to consider the importance that teachers place on digital note-taking compared to analogue environments, as well as the impact this has on student learning.

Keywords: note-taking, university teachers, scientific field, higher education teaching, approaches to teaching, approaches to learning

Introduction

Within the framework of examining teaching approaches as a dichotomy (Prosser & Trigwell, 1999) it is possible to establish the student-focused approach versus the teacher-focused approach. These two approaches can be viewed as traditional (teacher-focused approach) versus modern teaching approach (student-focused approach). The student-focused approach involves a departure from traditional teacher responsibilities and encourages students to take greater responsibility for their own learning (McCabe & O'Connor, 2014). The studies correlating the teachers' teaching approach and the students' learning approach have shown that the student-focused teaching approach is associated with a deep approach to learning, while the teacher-focused approach is linked to a surface approach to student learning. It has also been found that there is a correlation between the students' deep approach to learning and higher learning outcomes (Prosser & Trigwell, 1999). Revised ATI instrument besides the development of ATI has also shown as a useful trigger tool in 'phenomenographic pedagogic' discussion (Trigwell, Prosser & Ginns 2005). The aim of the phenomenographic

pedagogy process is to raise teachers' awareness of their thinking and practice and how variation in this practice might be related to their students' approaches to learning. Raising teachers' awareness is achieved through a process in which teachers reflect on their teaching approaches while weighing them against alternate approaches (Trigwell et al, 2005:350). During the implementation of our research on the Approaches to Teaching Inventory, one of the most frequently commented items by the university teachers was related to taking notes during the educational process. Note-taking during lectures is considered an active learning method aimed at helping students record, clarify, organize and understand information highlighted during lectures, as well as improving the learning process and student achievement (Bonner & Holliday, 2006). Over the years, numerous studies have confirmed that note-taking can have positive effects on learning (Nye, Crooks, Powley & Tripp, 1984; Kobayashi, 2006; Jansen, Lakens & Ijsselsteijn, 2017), and working on improving notes can have a significant impact on students' learning approach, leading to a deeper processing of course content (Castelló, & Monereo, 2005). Much research is often conducted by placing students in various situations related to note-taking during lectures, followed by measuring their performance in immediate and/or delayed testing (Di Vesta & Gray, 1972; Makany, Kemp & Dror, 2009; Bohay, Blakely, Tamplin & Radvansky, 2011; Artz, Johnson, Robson & Taengnoi, 2020). Additionally, students' experiences have been examined to better understand their note-taking habits and the meanings they attribute to them (Badger, White, Sutherland & Haggis, 2001; Bonner & Holliday, 2006; Morehead, Dunlosky, Rawson, Blasiman & Hollis, 2019; Witherby & Tauber, 2019).

Considering that a large number of previous studies focus on students, we conducted this research to examine the perspective of the university teachers, starting from the standpoint that their role is also significant in keeping students'

note-taking. The research aims to assess the importance teachers attach to students taking notes in comparison to copying teachers' notes, as well as examining the influence of various personal and contextual variables that we believed could potentially influence the differences in the teachers' responses.

The first part of the paper presents the theoretical framework, showcasing the importance of note-taking and providing a brief overview of the directions of previous research. This is followed by the methodology section presenting information about the sample and research procedure, the instrument used, and the research objective. The subsequent section presents the most significant research results, followed by a discussion. Finally, concluding considerations with recommendations for further research are provided.

The importance of note-taking and research directions

Research indicates two fundamental ways in which note-taking can contribute to learning (Di Vesta & Gray, 1972): encoding and external storage. The advantage of encoding (also known as process benefit) refers to the learning resulting from the act of taking notes, while the benefit of external storage (also called product benefit) pertains to the advantages derived from studying/reviewing the notes (Bui, Myerson & Hale, 2013). Di Vesta and Gray (1972) emphasize the significance of note-taking serving the encoding function, as it involves the learner actively engaging with the material, connecting it to the existing cognitive structure and making it meaningful. The note-taking process involves investing cognitive effort, as students go through the cycles of understanding the lecture content, identifying key points; connecting content to prior knowledge and materials; paraphrasing or summarizing; and transforming it into written form (Jansen et al., 2017). On the other hand, note-taking allows students to store information outside of their own memory, enabling them to

revisit, review, process, conceptualize, and memorize it (Friedman, 2014; Peeverly & Wolf, 2019).

Based on a literature review, Jansen et al. (2017) identify several research directions on factors influencing note-taking, including individual differences in cognitive abilities; methods of student note-taking, and characteristics of lectures. Note-taking involves a complex process where various mental processes, such as listening, understanding, identifying the key points, and coordinating writing or typing, occur simultaneously under time constraints (Friedman, 2014), which can be overly cognitively demanding for some students, suggesting that the note-taking may not benefit all students (Jansen et al., 2017). In the contemporary context, the development of digital technologies and the increasing use of digital devices and tools during the teaching process add complexity to the note-taking topic. Therefore, numerous studies explore whether note-taking methods have changed and to what extent it has affected their functions, with inconsistent results (Kim, Turner & Pérez-Quñones, 2009; Mueller & Oppenheimer, 2014; Stacy & Cain, 2015; Morehead et al., 2019; Witherby & Tauber, 2019; Artz et al., 2020). Digital devices provide the opportunity to record more information during lectures, but, there is doubt that typing notes may lead to more literal content recording, potentially lacking the encoding function. Additionally, the academic field to which the students belong needs consideration, as certain types of information, such as graphical data, can be challenging to capture through digital devices (Kim et al., 2009). Research on student note-taking methods has also focused on analyzing different characteristics of student notes and their correlation with learning outcomes. These characteristics include the quantity of notes (Nye et al., 1984); the use of linear versus non-linear techniques for organizing notes (Piolat, Olive & Kellogg, 2005; Makany et al., 2009); different note-taking strategies (Chen, 2019), revealing that strategy usage varies among

students of different scientific fields, potentially related to the content of academic subjects; and more.

The note-taking process can be influenced by certain lecture characteristics, such as the delivery style, lecture speed, and structure, which relate to how well different parts of the lecture are interconnected (Jansen et al., 2017). In this regard, the role of the teacher in organizing lectures – organization, pace, emotional tone, intonation – and actions during lectures – such as providing prepared material; writing on the board; highlighting and/or repeating important information, summarizing complex information, significantly affecting students' ability to take notes (DeZure, Kaplan & Deerman, 2001). One of the key questions in the literature concerns whether possessing complete teacher notes helps or hinders learning. Concerns revolve around the possibility that students might overly rely on external aids, potentially leading to passivity in lectures and absenteeism (Kim et al., 2009; Stacy & Cain, 2015). In this way, active learning may be reduced since students are provided with all the information and are not directly involved in the process of identification, collection and organization of information through note-taking (Brazeau, 2006). On the other hand, note-taking during a lecture requires cognitive effort, and students may struggle to capture all important information and/or may record it incorrectly. One strategy is to provide students with only a lecture outline instead of a complete set of slides or teacher notes. It is essential to ensure that materials are not so extensive that students decide not to take notes during class, as this could result in a crucial aspect of learning being missed (Friedman, 2014; Stacy & Cain, 2015).

Method

Sample and procedure

The research sample was purposefully selected and consisted of 317 teachers and associates of the University of Novi Sad. A detailed overview of the characteristics of the sample in terms of gender, scientific field, teaching academic title, level of education, group size, years of service and age of the teachers is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Detailed overview of sample characteristics (n=317)

The variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	191	60.3
	Female	125	39.4
Scientific field	Natural Sciences	63	19.9
	Humanities & Social Sciences	149	47
	Medical Sciences	35	11
	Technical & Technological Sciences	63	19.9
	Arts	7	2.2
Academic title	Teaching Associate	11	3.5
	Assistant	57	18
	Assistant with a PhD	15	4.7
	Assistant Professor	72	22.7
	Associate Professor	74	23.3
	Full professor	88	27.8

Level of education	Bachelor's studies	294	92.7
	Master's studies	22	6.9
Work experience of teachers	Less than 5 years	54	17
	5-10 years	65	20.5
	More than 10 years	197	62.1
Number of students in a group	Less than 30 students	173	54.6
	From 30 to 100 students	97	30.6
	More than 100 students	47	14.8
Age of the teachers	Less than 35 years	91	28.7
	35-45 years	106	33.4
	More than 45 years	120	37.9

After obtaining the author's consent for to use of the questionnaire, the instrument was translated into the Serbian language and prepared in printed form for completion. Data collection was conducted from November 23, 2022, to December 24, 2022, at the workplaces of teachers and associates. Before participating, the participants were informed about the research purpose and provided with the instructions for completing the questionnaire. Participation in the research was entirely anonymous and voluntary.

Instrument

In the research, the Approaches to Teaching Inventory - ATI (Prosser & Trigwell, 1999) instrument was used. The revised questionnaire consisted of 22 items, with 11 items focusing on the conceptual change and student-focused approach, while the remaining 11 items centered on information transmission and were directed at the teacher-focused approach. The item related to note-taking is defined in a way that aligns with a student-focused teaching approach, but

potential disagreement may indicate a teacher-focused instructional approach. This item serves as an appropriate means to analyze note-taking and the dominant teaching approach. Since teachers can apply different approaches to teaching in different subjects, within this research it was necessary for university teachers to give answers with only one subject in mind. The item: *It is better for students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine*, examines university teachers' attitudes towards student note-taking during lectures versus providing ready-made notes and can be linked to the student-focused approach which aims to conceptual change and this is the scope of our paper. The participants evaluated the items on a five-point Likert-type scale, the value of which ranged from 1 - rarely or never, to 5 - almost always or always.

The aim of the research

The research aims to examine the importance that the university teachers attribute to their students' note-taking compared to copying teacher notes, as well as investigating the (non)existence of differences among teacher responses in relation to the variables such as gender, academic title, level of study, size of the group for a specific subject, years of service and the age of the teachers.

Results

Table 2 presents the results of the descriptive statistical analysis for the item examining university teachers' perspectives on the importance of students generating their own notes during lectures, as opposed to relying on the notes provided by the teacher.

Table 2. *Descriptive indicators of the item*

Item	M	SD	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>
It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine.	3.52	1.30	1	5

The data show that for the statement – 'It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine,' an average value of 3.52 suggests a tendency towards preferring students taking their own notes, but this preference is not strongly pronounced. The variability in responses indicates the existence of differing opinions among teachers.

Variables with significant differences in teacher responses

To investigate the existence of differences in the responses of the university teachers with respect to their field of science, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied. The obtained results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. *Differences in the teachers' responses based on their field of science*

Item	Scientific field	M	SD	F(df)	p
It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine.	Natural Sciences	3.34	1.28	2.43 (4,309)	.048
	Humanities & Social Sciences	3.67	1.31		
	Medical Sciences	3.14	1.29		
	Technical & Technological Sciences	3.65	1.22		
	Arts	2.67	1.37		

The application of the one-way analysis of variance revealed a significant effect of the field of science to which teachers belong on the responses within the item ($F(4, 309) = 2.43; p < .05$). Subsequent comparisons conducted using the LSD test indicate that the teachers belonging to the field of social sciences and humanities achieve significantly higher scores on the given item compared to the teachers from the field of medical sciences.

The one-way analysis of variance was also applied to examine the existence of differences in responses in relation to the age of the teachers. The obtained results are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. *Differences in responses based on the teachers' age*

Item	Age	M	SD	F(df)	<i>p</i>
It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine.	Less than 35	3.57	1.24	4.08 (2, 311)	.018
	35-45 years	3.79	1.15		
	More than 45	3.29	1.41		

The application of the one-way analysis of variance revealed a significant effect of the teachers' age on the differences in responses to the item: 'It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine' ($F(2, 311) = 4.08, p < .05$). Subsequent comparisons using the LSD test determined that teachers younger than 35 years achieve significantly higher scores compared to teachers older than 45 years.

Variables without significant differences in teacher responses

- By applying the t-test for independent samples, it has been established that there are no significant differences in the responses of male and female teachers.
- No significant differences were found in responses based on the level of study at which the teachers teach.
- Using the one-way Analysis of Variance, no significant differences were found in the responses based on the academic titles of the teachers, thereby eliminating the need for further analyses to compare between different groups.
- No significant differences were found in the responses relative to the teachers' years of teaching experience, thus negating the need for additional comparative analyses among groups.
- No significant differences were observed in the responses based on the size of the student groups within the given subject, thereby negating the necessity for further analyses and comparisons among groups.

Discussion

The descriptive indicators of the item 'It is better for the students in this course to generate their own notes rather than copy mine' show a mild tendency among the teachers towards the attitude that it's better for the students to write their own notes rather than copying theirs. Using the one-way analysis of variance, it was found that the teachers in social sciences and humanities achieved significantly higher scores on this item compared to the teachers in medical sciences.

The observed differences in responses might be attributed to the varied teaching approaches of teachers from different disciplines. The research indicates that the teachers in "hard" sciences often employ the teacher-focused approach, while those in "soft" sciences lean more towards the student-focused approach (Lindblom-Ylänne, Trigwell, Nevgi & Ashwin, 2006). Additionally, previous research suggests that the students in social sciences and humanities generally show a greater inclination towards a deeper approach to learning (Beaten, Kyndt, Struyven & Dochy, 2010). This data might stem from the nature of content in certain disciplines. In social sciences and humanities, the emphasis is often on the overall context during lectures, requiring students to invest more time and effort in identifying key ideas. Consequently, their note-taking methods differ from those of students in other disciplines (Chen, 2019). It's possible that the content of social sciences and humanities is more conducive to independent note-taking compared to the content of medical sciences, which consists of more concrete and procedural information. This may make it harder to take notes independently, leading teachers to prefer relying on prepared materials. The observed difference also might be associated with the tendency of social sciences and humanities teachers to focus on developing critical thinking and soft skills. In contrast, medical science teachers might give more importance to the development of

professional skills. This hypothesis necessitates further research to gain a better understanding. Considering that the Faculty of Medicine offers a degree program in English, it would be important to investigate whether teachers' attitudes towards note-taking differ in this context, especially since some studies have focused on the importance of note-taking in students' non-native language (Badger et al., 2001).

The obtained results may point to certain tendencies in teachers' attitudes in relation to their academic field, as well as to the diversity of views within each field. Table 2 clearly shows that within each educational field, there is a wide range of responses. For example, although social sciences and humanities have the highest average scores, there is still variability in attitudes among teachers in this area. This variability might be due to the specifics of different faculties, courses, and subjects within that field, as well as other factors.

A positive attitude towards note-taking during lectures is also important from the perspective of organizing the lecture itself. Other research supports the importance of teachers organizing lectures with the provision of conditions for quality note-taking in mind. For instance, a study found that the most common responses to the question "I would make better notes if..." included "the professor speaks more slowly," "I write faster," and "I better recognize what's important." This highlights the significance of certain strategies that teachers should adopt to assist students in the cognitively demanding process of note-taking (Peverly & Wolf, 2019). In the literature, two factors are particularly noted as having a strong impact on students' ability to take notes: pace, which encompasses the speed of the lecture, the amount and complexity of information delivered; and signaling, which includes verbal and visual cues for emphasis, structure, and interconnections (DeZure, et al., 2001). In an earlier study by Isaacs (1994), it was found that most teachers emphasize the importance of note-taking during

lectures, but they vary in the significance they attribute to different functions of notes. The teachers identified key functions of note-taking as providing a basis for further learning, helping students remember lecture content, serving as a basis for review, and enabling students to understand the structure of the subject. Therefore, it's important to consider that teachers attribute different meanings to note-taking, influencing their approach to lecture organization. Further analyses are necessary to understand teachers' perspectives and practices regarding note-taking.

An interesting finding of the research is that younger teachers score higher on the analyzed item. This finding might be explained by the tendency of younger teachers to favor student-focused teaching, which encourages students to be active participants in the learning process and allows them more autonomy in determining what is important in the subject matter. This approach could also influence the greater emphasis they place on students' independent note-taking. Stacy & Cain (2015) also emphasize that teachers are shifting from traditional classroom content delivery modes to more student-focused approaches. This shift towards increasing student responsibility for their own learning may have implications for the practice of independent note-taking. Furthermore, considering that previous research indicates younger teachers may have more positive attitudes towards the use of technology in higher education (Guillén-Gámez & Mayorga-Fernández, 2020), another hypothesis worth investigating through further research is whether younger teachers more actively encourage the use of digital devices and applications for note-taking among students.

Concluding Considerations

The significance of studying note-taking stems from research indicating that the majority of students engage in taking and using notes both during and

after the teaching process (Morehead et al., 2019; Peverly & Wolf, 2019). While note-taking might be considered an activity involving a lower level of cognitive engagement (Biggs, 1999), there is a growing body of research associating it with cognitive processing (Peverly, et al., 2007) and cognitive load (Piolat et al., 2005; Jansen et al., 2017). This research emphasizes the significant positive effects that note-taking can have on learning processes and outcomes. Regardless of the adopted educational paradigm, whether teacher-focused or student-focused, note-taking holds a significant place in the teaching process. However, variations can be studied in relation to whether students should take their own notes (whether digital or analog) or whether it is better for teachers to provide prepared notes. In this sense, the aim of this research was to examine the importance that university teachers attribute to students' note-taking as opposed to providing them with prepared notes, while considering various personal and contextual variables.

The research results indicate that, generally, teachers demonstrate a moderately positive attitude towards students' note-taking. Significant differences in attitudes were found based on the scientific field of the teachers, with those in social sciences and humanities placing greater importance on students' note-taking compared to teachers in medical sciences. This could be due to different teaching approaches and the nature of the subject content in these areas. It was also found that younger teachers place greater importance on student notes, which may reflect their inclination towards contemporary pedagogical trends that advocate for increased student engagement and responsibility in the learning process. The findings represent an important starting point in examining the significance that teachers attribute to student note-taking. They also highlight the complexity of attitudes and the need for further research to better understand this topic and to enable the generalization of the obtained results.

A limitation of the conducted research is the use of only one item and its generality, as well as the lack of items pertaining to digital note-taking. In future research, it would be significant to compare analog and digital note-taking. This could potentially highlight the greater importance of variables such as gender, age, academic field, level of teaching, teaching experience, and group size, which were also tested in this study. If the items from our research were compared in digital versus analog environments, it is likely that these variables would prove to be more significant. Also, the research should be supplemented by simultaneously examining the perspectives and practices of both teachers and students. This opens up the question of the different stages in note-taking and what students do with their notes after lectures. Nevertheless, our research does offer insights into the differences associated with belonging to a certain academic field, as well as the dependency of responses on the age of the respondents. This is significant in the current phase of research within our academic community, where there is a lack of systematic studies on this topic.

References

- Artz, B., Johnson, M., Robson, D., & Taengnoi, S. (2020). Taking notes in the digital age: Evidence from classroom random control trials. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 51(2), 103-115.
- Badger, R., White, G., Sutherland, P., & Haggis, T. (2001). Note perfect: an investigation of how students view taking notes in lectures. *System*, 29(3), 405-417.
- Baeten, M., Kyndt, E., Struyven, K., & Dochy, F. (2010). Using student-centred learning environments to stimulate deep approaches to learning: Factors encouraging or discouraging their effectiveness. *Educational research review*, 5(3), 243-260.
- Biggs, J. (1999). What the student does: Teaching for enhanced learning. *Higher education research & development*, 18(1), 57-75.

- Bohay, M., Blakely, D. P., Tamplin, A. K., & Radvansky, G. A. (2011). Note taking, review, memory, and comprehension. *The American journal of psychology*, *124*(1), 63-73.
- Bonner, J. M., & Holliday, W. G. (2006). How college science students engage in note-taking strategies. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching: The Official Journal of the National Association for Research in Science Teaching*, *43*(8), 786-818.
- Brazeau, G. A. (2006). Handouts in the classroom: is note taking a lost skill?. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, *70*(2).
- Bui, D. C., Myerson, J., & Hale, S. (2013). Note-taking with computers: Exploring alternative strategies for improved recall. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *105*(2), 299.
- Castelló, M., & Monereo, C. (2005). Students' note-taking as a knowledge-construction tool. *L1-Educational Studies in Language and Literature*, *5*, 265-285.
- Chen, P. H. (2019). In-class and after-class lecture note-taking strategies. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, *22*(3), 245-260.
- DeZure, D., Kaplan, M., & Deerman, M. A. (2001). Research on student notetaking: Implications for faculty and graduate student instructors. *CRLT Occasional Papers*, *16*, 1-7.
- Di Vesta, F. J., & Gray, G. S. (1972). Listening and note taking. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *63*(1), 8-14.
- Friedman, M. C. (2014). Notes on note-taking: Review of research and insights for students and instructors. *Harvard Initiative for Learning and Teaching*, 1-34.
- Guillén-Gámez, F. D., & Mayorga-Fernández, M. J. (2020). Identification of variables that predict teachers' attitudes toward ICT in higher education for teaching and research: A study with regression. *Sustainability*, *12*(4), 1312.
- Isaacs, G. (1994). Lecturing practices and note-taking purposes. *Studies in Higher Education*, *19*(2), 203-216.
- Jansen, R. S., Lakens, D., & IJsselsteijn, W. A. (2017). An integrative review of the cognitive costs and benefits of note-taking. *Educational Research Review*, *22*, 223-233.

- Kim, K., Turner, S. A., & Pérez-Quiñones, M. A. (2009). Requirements for electronic note taking systems: A field study of note taking in university classrooms. *Education and Information Technologies, 14*, 255-283.
- Kobayashi, K. (2006). Combined Effects of Note-Taking/-Reviewing on Learning and the Enhancement through Interventions: A meta-analytic review. *Educational Psychology, 26*(3), 459-477.
- Lindblom-Ylänne, S., Trigwell, K., Nevgi, A., & Ashwin, P. (2006). How approaches to teaching are affected by discipline and teaching context. *Studies in Higher education, 31*(03), 285-298.
- Makany, T., Kemp, J., & Dror, I. E. (2009). Optimising the use of note-taking as an external cognitive aid for increasing learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 40*(4), 619-635.
- McCabe, A., & O'Connor, U. (2014). Student-centred learning: the role and responsibility of the lecturer. *Teaching in Higher Education, 19*(4), 350-359.
- Morehead, K., Dunlosky, J., Rawson, K. A., Blasiman, R., & Hollis, R. B. (2019). Note-taking habits of 21st century college students: implications for student learning, memory, and achievement. *Memory, 27*(6), 807-819.
- Mueller, P. A., & Oppenheimer, D. M. (2014). The pen is mightier than the keyboard: Advantages of longhand over laptop note taking. *Psychological science, 25*(6), 1159-1168.
- Nye, P. A., Crooks, T. J., Powley, M., & Tripp, G. (1984). Student note-taking related to university examination performance. *Higher Education, 13*, 85-97.
- Peeverly, S. T., & Wolf, A. D. (2019). Note-taking. In J. Dunlosky & K. A. Rawson (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of cognition and education* (pp. 320–355). Cambridge University Press.
- Peeverly, S. T., Ramaswamy, V., Brown, C., Sumowski, J., Alidoost, M., & Garner, J. (2007). What predicts skill in lecture note taking?. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 99*(1), 167.
- Piolat, A., Olive, T., & Kellogg, R. T. (2005). Cognitive effort during note taking. *Applied cognitive psychology, 19*(3), 291-312.
- Prosser & Trigwell (1999). *Understanding learning and teaching: The experience in higher education*. Buckingham, UK: SRHE and Open University Press.
- Stacy, E. M., & Cain, J. (2015). Note-taking and handouts in the digital

- age. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 79(7).
- Trigwell, K., Prosser, M., & Ginns, P. (2005). Phenomenographic pedagogy and a revised approaches to teaching inventory. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 24(4), 349-360.
- Witherby, A. E., & Tauber, S. K. (2019). The current status of students' note-taking: Why and how do students take notes?. *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 8(2), 139-153.

Acknowledgements

The text was created within the project "Pedagogical, Psychological, and Sociological Dimensions of Improving the Quality of Higher Education: Opportunities and Challenges." To implement this project, a portion of the funds was provided by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research of Vojvodina, through Decision No. 142-451-3379/2023-02.